

NFDI4Earth

NFDI4Earth Report

Analysis of online survey on incentives for FAIR and open data practices

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Executive summary

To better understand the current attitudes and practices surrounding FAIR and open data practices, an online survey was conducted, targeting researchers in the German Earth System Sciences community. 114 completed answers were considered in the analysis of the online survey.

Current engagement in FAIR and open data practices

“Citing data, software, and samples in your publications” is the most often exercised FAIR and open data practice, consistent with the fact that citation of journal articles or books is deeply embedded in research practice since decades as part of good scientific practice. Inclusion of a data availability statements (DAS) in journal publications is the second most often exercised practice, pointing to the effectiveness of obligations in journal submission policies. “Preparing, using and updating data management plans” is the least exercised practice, although using data management plans (DMPs) are increasingly expected or mandatory demanded by research funding organisations. About half of the participants of the online survey are engaged in teaching and training activities on FAIR and open data practices. PhD students are very rarely, and professors are very often engaged in such activities.

Motivators to perform FAIR and open data practices, drivers and barriers for data sharing

Better institutional support for FAIR and open data practices as well as more scientific recognition via dataset citation metrics are the strongest **motivators to perform FAIR and open data practices** more often. Only few participants think that awards for these practices are strong motivators.

The most important **drivers for data publication** are the perception that it improves science as a whole. This is contrasted by extrinsic drivers, such as requirements from publishers, funders, institutions, and data sharing norms, ranking lower.

The most important **reason for not sharing data** is the consideration that the data are not suitable for sharing. Fear that somebody else may publish earlier than the data originator on the data is another important reason for not sharing data.

Conclusions and implications for NFDI4Earth

NFDI4Earth should strengthen motivators for FAIR & open data practices in general and, in particular, for data publication, that are of high importance of survey participants.

Barriers to data sharing of high importance to survey participants may be assessed in order to identify targeted future actions to phase out disincentivising environments and structures.

NFDI4Earth might form strategic partnerships with partners like academic societies or the FID GEO for joint projects to improve the adoption of FAIR and open data practice.

NFDI4Earth may concentrate on training and education on data sharing and the use of DMPs as well as working together with NFDI4Earth member institutions and other partners to promote the introduction of data sharing policies and to strengthen existing ones.

NFDI4Earth member institutions should take advantage of NFDI4Earth-developed instruments, e. g. the Help Desk, in providing better assistance and infrastructure to its researchers.

Development of data citation metrics and the recognition of FAIR and open data practices should be supported by NFDI4Earth to drive the much-needed cultural change.

Colleagues as role models are important: NFDI4Earth member institutions should develop programs that make researchers that engage in FAIR and open data practice more visible.

This work is part of the work in the measure M4.2 "Towards a Cultural Change in Earth System Sciences Research Data Management" of the NFDI-Consortium 4Earth.

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1 Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of scientific research, the principles of fairness and openness in research data management have gained significant prominence. To better understand the current attitudes and practices surrounding these principles, an online survey was conducted, targeting researchers in the German Earth System Sciences community. This report sheds light on the perspectives and experiences of researchers in relation to FAIR (Wilkinson *et al.* 2016) and open research data practices.

The survey aimed to capture a comprehensive view of the existing practices, challenges, and opportunities associated with FAIR and open data practices in general and with the sharing of research data in particular. Participants were asked to provide insights into their current practices and into reasons that would motivate them to engage in these practices more often. By analysing these responses, common trends can be identified and pinpoint areas emerge where improvements are needed to foster a more collaborative and transparent research environment.

This report provides actionable recommendations for institutions and for the NFDI4Earth to support researchers to enhance the fairness and openness of research data. Ultimately, the goal is to contribute to the ongoing dialogue on improving FAIR and open data practices, thereby advancing the overall quality and integrity of scientific research. This analysis of the online survey includes the results of the survey, which have been published already earlier (Hübner 2024).

The FAIR principles were formulated to guide researchers to make their data more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable, thereby supporting data sharing (Wilkinson *et al.* 2016). These principles are recommended as a tool to bring awareness to the types of actions that can improve the practice of data publication for all research disciplines, including the Earth Sciences (Kinkade and Shepherd 2021). Additionally, the promotion of the release of data, including geoscience data (Wildman and Lewis 2022), as 'open data' helps eliminate many barriers that would otherwise hinder data reuse.

Applied together, the principles of FAIR and open data prioritise data sharing and are effective approaches for engaging researchers and fostering sound data practices from the very start (Higman *et al.* 2019). Essentially, FAIR and open data practices means that research data (including e.g. code and physical samples) are well managed throughout the data life cycle, according to the FAIR principles, and are shared publicly under the maxim „as open as possible, as closed as necessary“.

In practice, for researchers FAIR and open data practices include:¹

- Depositing research outputs (e.g., data, software, physical sample information, etc.) in trustworthy, community-accepted, FAIR-aligned repositories.
- Fully documenting each data set in the metadata, which may include descriptive information about the context, quality and condition, or characteristics of the data.
- Citation of data, software, and other products created or reused for your research in your publications.
- Including a data availability statement in your journal publications.
- Preparing, using, and updating data management plans.
- Educating colleagues in practices that enable open and FAIR research outputs.
- Supporting development of open and FAIR standards and practices in your institutions and organisations, in academic societies, and in scholarly publishing as authors, reviewers, and editors.

Institutions, academic societies and community networks may support FAIR and open data practices by:

- Providing regular education and outreach to their communities regarding these principles and practices.
- Promoting open and FAIR data activities as important criteria in promotion, awards, and honours.
- Establishing research data policies that describe a transparent framework of processes, expectations, responsibilities, and obligations for the handling of research data in an organisation.
- Providing other credit and recognition for researchers that are following open and FAIR data practices and encourage others to include such recognition as part of regular career advancement.

1.1 The survey

The survey was structured in the way that it started with questions about the status of the participant, the institutional affiliation and the disciplinary field of work (see below). Then, FAIR and open data practices were addressed: about the general relevance of FAIR and open data practices, the engagement in FAIR and open data practices in research and teaching/education activities, and about incentives that would motivate participants to perform FAIR and open data practices more often. This was followed by two questions about data sharing: drivers of data

¹ The text for the bullet points is adapted from the Enabling FAIR Data „[Commitment Statement in the Earth, Space, and Environmental Sciences](#)“.

sharing and reasons for not to share data. The survey was designed to take approximately 10 min to answer.

1. Status / Institutional affiliation / Field of work

2. FAIR and open data practices

- How often do you engage in certain FAIR and open data practices?
- Research
- Teaching/Education
- Motivations to perform FAIR and open data practices more often?

3. Data sharing

- How important are the following drivers to share your data?
- How important are the following reasons to not share your data?

A pretest of the survey was conducted with four researchers and two persons from a university research data management team and resulted in valuable feedback especially on the clarity of the questions.

The request to participate in the online survey was distributed in October 2023. It was sent via Email to all NFDI4Earth consortium members contact persons and, as far as know, to their institutional research data management teams of participant institutions. This included the request to circulate this information in the relevant sections and departments of the respective institution. The invitation to participate in the online survey was also circulated via the NFDI4Earth email list, in the NFDI4Earth newsletter and was prominently placed on the NFDI4Earth website. The online survey was open until 17 December 2023.

1.2 Participants

Overall, 151 persons participated in the online survey. 115 participants completed the survey, however, one of these answers stemmed obviously from the test phase of the survey and was excluded from the analysis. Therefore, 114 completed answers were considered in the analysis of the online survey.

2 Status / Institutional affiliation / Field of work

2.1 Status

The largest (professional) status group of survey participants is “postdocs” (Fig. 1). 42 participants indicated to be postdocs in the survey and 32 persons checked “other” and added a job description in the free text field. However, 27 participants of the group “other” indicated to be researchers, senior scientists, „wissenschaftliche(r) Mitarbeiter(in)“, or alike (Tab. 1). This group of 27 was shifted to the group of postdocs, because “postdoc” in this survey encompasses all career stages between persons with finished dissertation and professor. This results in 69 persons (60,5%) to belong to the group of “postdocs”. The second largest group of participants were PhD students (n=28; 24,6%), followed by professors (n=11; 9,6%). 4 participants were Data manager/Data steward, 1 indicated to be in a leadership position, 1 participant was lecturer and 1 was BSc/MSc student.

Figure 1: Status groups of participants of the online survey.

Table 1: Free text entries for the field “My status: I respond to this survey... [Other]”. *the original quote was substituted by „Leadership position” for privacy protection reasons. “x” indicates that this participant’s answer was moved to the category “postdoc”.

My status: I respond to this survey... [Other]: free text entries	moved to category “postdoc”
Data Manager	
data manager	
Data Steward	
„Leadership position”*	
lecturer	
research associate	x
research group lead (bet. postdoc and prof)	x
Research Scientist	x
Research Staff	x
Researcher	x
scientific employee	x
scientific employee (wissenschaftliche(r) Mitarbeiter(in))	x
Scientist	x
scientist	x
Senior postdoc	x
Senior research scientist	x
Senior Researcher	x
senior researcher	x
Senior Researcher	x
senior researcher / project manager	x
senior scientist	x
staff scientist	x
wiss. Mitarbeiter	x
Wissenschaftliche Mitarbeiterin	x

2.2 Institutional affiliation

49 participants work at a non-university institution, 59 participants work at universities. 6 participants stated different affiliations in “other” (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Bar chart of answers to the question about the institutional affiliation.

Table 2: Free text entries for the field “I work at ... [Other]”.

I work at ... [Other]: free text entries
Federal Agency
government institute
I work at bot types of institutes above.
KIT
National Hydrological Service
research facility

2.3 Discipline

A broad range of disciplines is covered by the survey participants (Fig. 3). Most participants indicated to belong to the discipline “Physics and Chemistry of the Atmosphere” (n=26; 22,8%), followed by “Geology, Engineering Geology, Palaeontology” (n=15; 13,2%) and “Physics of the Earth's Body” and “Mineralogy, Petrology and Geochemistry” (each n=12; 10,5%) (see all disciplines in Tab. 3). Free text entries of the group “other” are shown in Tab. 4. Few of the entries in Tab. 4 could have shifted easily to pre-specified disciplines (e.g. Geophysics), but with many others, this would have proven difficult. For this reason, no reorganisation of disciplinary affiliations was carried out.

Figure 3: Bar chart of answers to the question “Which Earth System Sciences (ESS) field is your major field of work?”.

Table 3: Summary of the answers for the question “Which Earth System Sciences (ESS) field is your major field of work?”.

Discipline	[%]	n
Physics and Chemistry of the Atmosphere	22,8	26
Geology, Engineering Geology, Palaeontology	13,2	15
Physics of the Earth's Body	10,5	12
Mineralogy, Petrology and Geochemistry	10,5	12
Physics, Chemistry and Biology of the Sea	7,9	9
Geodesy, Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing, Geoinformatics, Cartography	7,9	9
Physical Geography	4,4	5
Planetary and Solar System Sciences	4,4	5
Hydrogeology, Hydrology, Limnology, Water Chemistry	2,6	3
Human Geography	0	0
Other	15,8	18

Table 4: Free text entries for the field “Which Earth System Sciences (ESS) field is your major field of work? [Other]”.

Which Earth System Sciences (ESS) field is your major field of work? [Other]: free text entries

biogeochemistry
 Biogeosciences
 Climate Mitigation (Economics)
 Climate science
 Climate science of the atmosphere, ocean, and land cryosphere; modelling
 Computational science
 Cryosphere
 Crystallography, Solid state physics, Mineralogy
 Ecology
 Environmental Sciences
 ESS Data Science and Management
 Geophysics
 Glaciology, Geophysics
 Limnology and Ocean Sciences, Microbiology, Remote Sensing
 Palaeoclimate
 Physics of the Ocean
 Terrestrial biogeochemical cycles

2.4 Discussion

Postdocs, PhD-students and professors are by far the most prominent participants of the survey. This confirms that the main target group of the survey, researchers, has been successfully addressed to participate in the online survey.

Regarding institutional affiliation the results confirm that the survey participants stem from a variety of research institutions and that both universities and “non-university research institutions”, the major research institution members of the NFDI4Earth, are well represented.

Survey participants represent a broad variety of Earth System Sciences disciplines. However, there is a striking absence of participants from human geography. Outreach by NFDI4Earth should be increased in the future to get this discipline better represented and integrated into NFDI4Earth.

3 FAIR and open data practices

3.1 Importance to expand FAIR and open data practices

Figure 4: Bar chart of answers to the question “How important do you think the expansion of FAIR and open data practices is for research as a whole?”.

The expansion of FAIR and open data practices for research as a whole is “very important” or “important” for 96% of the participants (Fig. 4). There is no significant change in the pattern of answers with regard to the status information provided by survey participants” (Fig. 5). There are little variations of answer patterns with regard to different research disciplines. The strong increase of “very important” within the group of “other” is of little relevance because this group includes a lot of different disciplines (see Tab. 4).

This result confirms that FAIR and open data practices are considered relevant for the vast majority of researchers, covering all status groups and all disciplines. However, there might be some bias here since the participation in the online survey was voluntary and it cannot be excluded that people who do not consider expansion of FAIR and open data practices to be important or are agnostic towards such practices did just not take part in the survey in the first place.

Figure 5: Bar chart of answers to the question “How important do you think the expansion of FAIR and open data practices is for research as a whole?” combined with status information of the participants.

Figure 6: Bar chart of answers to the question “How important do you think the expansion of FAIR and open data practices is for research as a whole?” combined with disciplinary affiliation information of the participants.

Regarding the status of the survey participants (Fig. 5), the distribution of participant’s statuses in the categories “very important” and “important” is roughly identical. Regarding disciplines, there are marked differences: The discipline category “other” as well as “Mineralogy, Petrology and Geochemistry” is remarkably more represented in the category “very important” as compared to “important” (Fig. 6). This shows that researchers from the discipline “Mineralogy, Petrology and Geochemistry” stand out positively in considering the expansion of FAIR and open data practices being relevant.

3.2 Engagement with FAIR and open data practices

3.2.1 Results

Figure 7: Bar chart of answers to the question “When working with data, how often do you engage in the following FAIR and open data practices?” n<114 indicates that some participants clicked on the option “not applicable to me” (the latter is not shown in the bar chart). Example: “Depositing data and software in suitable repositories” had 107 participants that indicated their engagement frequency, 7 participants clicked on “not applicable to me”.

Figure 8: Bar chart of answers to the question “When working with data, how often do you engage in the following FAIR and open data practices?”, only answers “always” and “often”, ordered in terms of percentage of answers. n<114 indicates that some participants clicked on the option “not applicable to me” (not shown in the bar chart).

When working with data, how often do you engage in the following FAIR and open data practices?

Figure 9: Bar chart of answers to the question “When working with data, how often do you engage in the following FAIR and open data practices?”, only answers “always” and “often”, combined with status information of the participants.

3.2.2 Discussion

Citation

When considering only the categories “always” and “often” (Fig. 8), “Citing data, software, and samples in your publications” ranks highest (82 %). This may be due to the fact that citation is deeply embedded in research practice since decades as part of good scientific practice. Citing of data and software has started to become common practice in many disciplines, including Earth System Sciences, and one reason for that is that journal publishers allow and promote data and software citations, as a result on initiatives like e.g. COPDESS.²

Data availability statements

About 80 % of the participants include “always” and “often” a data availability statements (DAS) in journal publications (Fig. 8). Today, most journals in the Earth System Sciences request a DAS in submitted manuscripts and therefore it is no surprise that this practice is performed by such a high number of researchers. However, the quality of a data availability statement is variable with respect to supporting data sharing in reality: statements like “data availability upon (reasonable) request” turn out to be inefficient for supporting data sharing (Tedersoo

² <https://copdess.org/>

et al. 2021; Watson 2022). NFDI4Earth should address this issue in educational resources and programs for Earth System Sciences researchers and may be active, working together with Fachinformationsdienst Geowissenschaften, to approach Earth System Sciences academic societies (as journal publishers) to work towards an improved concept for to not accept data availability in the future.

Publication of research data

FAIR and open data practices ranking 3-5 when considering the answers “always” and “often” (Fig. 8) all relate to the publication of research data, and it is considered positive that about 70% of participants publish data in suitable repositories and licence them as openly as possible. As many as 58% declare that they provide the data publications with complete documentation. However, the author’s personal experience as a Liaison Librarian for the geosciences at the Freie Universität Berlin shows that self-perception of researchers and perception by others with regard to what is considered to be a complete documentation of research data may differ strongly in individual cases, indicating that there is still a lot of room for improvement and need for educational efforts.

Developing open and FAIR standards and practices

Strong engagement in “Supporting development of open and FAIR standards and practices in scholarly publishing as author, reviewer and editor” and “in your institution and organisation” is indicated by slightly less than 50% of respondents (“always” and “often”, Fig. 8). This engagement seems to be low when considering scholarly publishing, because most journals today promote FAIR and open data in submission guidelines. However, it is unclear how journals educate and prompt reviewers and editors to consider FAIR and open data when handling manuscripts. On the other hand, a strong engagement for open and FAIR standards and practices in “institutions and organisations” of 45% of participants is considered to be positive in general, because such an engagement is not directly related to research activities of scientists, but reflects the willingness of researchers to contribute to the positive development of their organisation or institution (with, eventually, also positive effects for their own scientific work).

Educating colleagues

Strong engagement in “Educating colleagues in practices that enable open and FAIR research outputs” is indicated by about 30% of respondents (Fig. 8). Such education may take place in different forms, for example as informal discussions in small research groups or in one-to-one conversations, or more formally, when a supervisor provides feedback to a PhD student or in routine team meetings. The development of the NFDI4Earth FAIRness and Openness Commitment (NFDI4Earth Consortium 2024) may be highlighted to play an important role as an instrument to spark conversation about the topic and advance the cultural change towards a world where FAIR and open data practices are just a matter of course. NFDI4Earth may relate

its Commitment statement strongly to the DFG's Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice - Code of Conduct (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft 2022) and join forces with the efforts of research institutions to implement the Code of Conducts in Earth System Sciences-related university departments.

Data management plans

Only 29% of respondents indicate strong engagement in "Preparing, using and updating data management plans" ("always" and "often", Fig. 8). This is surprising because using data management plans (DMPs) are increasingly expected or mandatory demanded by research funding organisations when applying for funding. In light of this result, NFDI4Earth may take focused action on the promotion of the preparation, use and update of DMPs to increase the understanding and usage of DMPs as a valuable tool in research data management.

Differences of status groups

The variations in the proportions of each status group variations (Fig. 9) appear to be so small that an interpretation does not seem meaningful.

3.3 FAIR and open research practices in teaching and training

Figure 10: Bar chart of answers to the question “In case you are designing curricula, teaching students or supervising PhD students, which of the following practices do you perform?”. Multiple answers possible. N=52 participants answered positively at least on one of the options 1-4; 61 participants of the online survey clicked on the option “not applicable to me” (the latter is not shown in the bar chart).

Table 5: Free text entries for the field “In case you are designing curricula, teaching students or supervising PhD students, which of the following practices do you perform?... [Other].”

Free text entries for question “In case you are designing curricula (...)

I am not teacher, only researcher

none

Recommend NFDI4Earth academy

While the previous question relates to research practices, the question “In case you are designing curricula, teaching students or supervising PhD students, which of the following practices do you perform?” relates to teaching and training activities on FAIR and open research

practices and data management. The results show that only about half of the participants of the online survey (n=52) are engaged in teaching and training activities on FAIR and open data practices (Fig. 10). When looking at the status of the participants that are engaged in these activities it is apparent that PhD students are very rarely, and professors are very often engaged. Postdoctoral researchers are equally engaged and not engaged in these activities.

The survey participants engaged in FAIR and open research practices in teaching and training very often advise or teach students how to share data and code (77%), as well as they are raising awareness and understanding of FAIR and open data (64%), but only 13% are involved in embracing FAIR and open data practices in a more structured way in teaching activities by developing curricula on the topic (Fig. 10). Curricula development is done mainly by postdocs (n=4). Also, two of the three data stewards/data managers participating in this online survey develop curricula on the topic, and only one out of 11 professors participating in this online survey develop curricula on the topic.

The results indicate that FAIR and open data practices in teaching and training are addressed with students and in undergraduate and graduate programs rather in an informal way than in a structured way by means of curricula teaching. This underpins the relevance of NFDI4Earth Measure 1.3 Education and Training Materials, where modular course materials and curricula are developed that can be integrated into existing university curricula to promote the topic of FAIR and open research practices and data management in students' curricula.

3.4 Motivators for FAIR and open data practices

3.4.1 Results

Figure 11: Bar chart of answers to the question “What would motivate you to perform FAIR and open data practices more often?”.

Figure 12: Bar chart of answers to the question “What would motivate you to perform FAIR and open data practices more often?”. Only answers “always” and “often”, ordered in terms of cumulative percentage.

What would motivate you to perform FAIR and open data practices more often?

Figure 13: Bar chart of answers to the question “What would motivate you to perform FAIR and open data practices more often?”. Only answers “always” and “often”, combined with status information of the participants

3.4.2 Discussion

Improved institutional advice, education and infrastructure

Better advice and education for FAIR and open data practices from institutions ranks highest as motivator for performing more FAIR and open data practices (75,5 %, Fig. 12), when considering only the answers “very strong motivator” and “strong motivator”.

There seem to be a lack of clarity regarding the specific requirements and expectations of research institutions and funders, which can lead to uncertainty and confusion among researchers. To address this, it is essential to provide clear and concise guidelines and standards for FAIR and open data practices, as well as to provide training and support for researchers to understand and implement these practices effectively.

There are already many different infrastructures in place that support researchers in FAIR and open research data management practices, e.g., see a lists in (Bernard *et al.* 2021) . However, there are major challenges ahead as these services are scattered and heterogeneous and only a few of them have a long-term perspective (Bernard *et al.* 2021). That may be the major reason why, researchers are calling for improved technical infrastructure to support the implementation of these practices. (71,0 %, Fig. 12). In line with this result, one of the major

goals of NFDI4Earth is the consolidation and harmonisation of research-data-related services in Earth System Sciences.

Data citation metrics

Data citation metrics are a highly motivating factor for researchers to adopt FAIR and open data practices, with 71% of respondents indicating that they would be more likely to engage in these practices if such metrics existed (Fig. 12). However, the development of suitable metrics is a significant challenge, as current metrics often rely on simplistic counts that fail to capture the quality and impact of research data. Determining the quality of research data sets is a complex task, and any metrics developed must ideally encompass a range of quality criteria and must ideally embrace all types of research data (and research software) publications (Castell *et al.* 2024).

However, it is also essential to consider the potential risks associated with quantitative metrics (Helmer *et al.* 2020). Any efforts to develop metrics for FAIR and open data practices must be approached with caution.

Role models

Colleagues as role models are important incentives, as the indicator “Fellow researchers that engage already in FAIR & open data practice” is ranking high (64,1%, Fig. 12). This may inform institutions to develop programs that make researchers that engage in FAIR and open data practice more visible.

One instrument towards this end is the introduction of data champions. Data champions may be researchers or employees who have excelled in the field of research data management and/or have experience that is groundbreaking for colleagues or can serve as a guide. Examples of Data Champions initiatives are present at many German and international universities already³. Additionally, institutions could feature research data publications of a research department on a departmental website in order to improve the visibility of data publications⁴. With this instrument, researchers may get better information about data publications of colleagues, fostering the notion that data publications are already a strong part of the publication culture of the department.

Policies from publishers, funders, and institutions

Stronger recommendations and/or requirements from journals/publishers for FAIR and open data practices are important incentives for 60,5% of the participants (Fig. 12). Publishers

³ E.g. <https://www.uni-bielefeld.de/ub/digital/forschungsdaten/data-champions/data-champions-netzwerk/>; <https://www.fdm.uni-hannover.de/de/data-champions>, <https://www.data.cam.ac.uk/intro-data-champions> (accessed 05 April 2025)

⁴ <https://www.geo.fu-berlin.de/forschung/forschungsdaten/Forschungsdaten-des-Fachbereichs/index.html> (accessed 05 April 2025)

and journals have begun to encourage, and even require, data sharing in recent years, and academic communities have increasingly adopted data availability statements as a way to indicate research data availability related to research articles (Jiao *et al.* 2024). However, requiring a DAS may not necessarily be enough to make data sharing a reality: a study in biology, health sciences and medicine journals showed that “even when authors indicate in their manuscript that they will share data upon request, the compliance rate is the same as for authors who do not provide the DAS, suggesting that the DAS may not be sufficient to ensure data sharing.” (Gabelica *et al.* 2022). Journal data policies should indeed be improved, as was shown by an analysis of 31 journals from the Earth sciences and from Biodiversity that are published by German learned societies or research institutions (Hübner 2020).

Stronger and/or more detailed funder requirements for FAIR and open data practices are important incentives for 59,7% of the participants (Fig. 12). This result may seem counterintuitive, given that many research funders already have strong requirements in place for FAIR and open data practices. For example, as of Summer 2023, the publication of FAIR research data is a rule (with reasonable exemptions) for scientists at German universities and non-university research institutions that (want to) receive funding from the DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft 2022)⁵. Also, for EU-funded research in the Horizon Europe programme compliance with the FAIR principles and Open Data exchange is a standard⁶. One possible explanation for this result is that researchers may feel that the current requirements are not being monitored and/or enforced consistently or effectively. Additionally, there may be a need for greater clarity and consistency in the requirements and expectations around FAIR and open data practices.

Stronger institutional research data policies are a “very strong motivator” or “strong motivator” for only 47,3% of the participants (Fig. 12). This result suggests that while institutional research data policies are an important factor in motivating researchers to adopt FAIR and open data practices, they are not as influential as other factors, such as stronger funder requirements or the availability of training and education.

A structured content analysis of research data policies of German research institutions is not

⁵ Guideline 13: Providing public access to research results: “As a rule, researchers make all results available as part of scientific/academic discourse. [...] Where possible and reasonable, this includes making the research data [...] available [...]. [...] whenever possible researchers make the research data and principal materials on which a publication is based available in recognized archives and repositories in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).” DFG’s “Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice” codex (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6472827>)

⁶ “In Horizon Europe, research data should be made open access by default and licensed under the latest version of CC BY (attribution required) or CC 0 (public domain), or equivalent. However, it is recognized that data should be ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’ and exceptions can be made when providing open access to data. [...] beneficiaries must explain in the DMP the legitimate exception(s) under which they choose to restrict access to (some of the) research data.” <https://www.openaire.eu/how-to-comply-with-horizon-europe-mandate-for-rdm> (accessed 05 April 2025)

available, but examples show that details in institutional research data policies may vary widely, see ,e.g.,. the Research Data Policy of Universität Bielefeld⁷ as an example for a rather concise policy and the Research Data Policy of Freie Universität Berlin (Freie Universität Berlin 2021) as an example for a more detailed policy.

One possible explanation for this result is that institutional research data policies may not be well-known or widely understood by researchers, or because they are not consistently enforced or monitored. Potential action for NFDI4Earth may be in the future in raising awareness of German research institutions about improved institutional research data policies, including using available suggestions for improved data policies (Hiemenz and Kuberek 2018; Arbeitskreis Open Science der Helmholtz-Gemeinschaft 2019; Helmholtz Association 2022; Llebot and Castillo 2023).

Career advantages

56% of the participants consider career advantages as a “very important” or “important” motivator (Fig. 12). Compared to other motivators in the survey, it ranks in the middle to lower range. However, this ranking position is somewhat ambiguous because this indicator is the only one in this set of indicators where more participants voted for “very strong motivator” rather than “strong motivator”. Considering only the share of participants that voted for “very important”, this indicator would rank much higher, at third place, implying that the ranking in the middle to lower range of the “very-important or important” ranking (Fig. 12) does not fully reflect the importance of this indicator as a motivator for FAIR and open data practices for the survey participants. However, answers about career-related indicators in the “data sharing” sections of this survey (see below) support the fact that researchers do consider career advantages a rather weak incentive: When asking for drivers for data sharing, “More citations of my research papers” and “Invitations to co-authorships from others that use my data” rank low. Closely related to the career advantages, FAIR and open data practices playing a stronger role in internal evaluations ranks low compared to other incentives addressed in this section.

The absence of current mechanisms in research institutions to structurally acknowledge FAIR and open data practices in career-related procedures may in part explain the survey result: researchers simply have no personal experience that these practices play any role for career advancement or research assessment, including institutional hiring, tenure, and promotion processes.

Research assessment has been under intense review internationally, with a critical look at its use of metrics and quantifiable indicators. Various declarations and guidelines have been put forward to promote more responsible and transparent evaluation and assessment methods (DORA Steering Committee 2012; Hicks *et al.* 2015; James Wilsdon *et al.* 2015). Especially

⁷ <https://www.uni-bielefeld.de/ub/digital/forschungsdaten/policy/> (accessed 05 April 2025)

CoARA has been recently strongly promoted, and many of the NFDI4Earth research institutions have signed the CoARA declaration and thus committed to review their research assessment procedures and develop measures to improve them (Tab. 6). Regarding FAIR and open data practices, considering FAIR data sets in research evaluation is one of the suggestions of the CoARA declaration.

Table 6: Number of NFDI4Earth member organisations that have signed CoARA and DORA statements.

	Number of institutions
CoARA	5
DORA	8

Awards

Only 37% of the participants think that awards for FAIR & open data practices are very important or important incentives. Research institutions, NFDI consortia or academic societies may take this result as a hint to design awards very carefully and not to overrate this instrument.

Differences of status groups

When considering responses of the different status groups to the question about motivators for FAIR and open data practices (Fig. 13) it is interesting to note that participants especially of the status group “professor” indicate that “awards for FAIR & open data practices” are a strong incentive (17%, Fig. 13). On the other hand, professors think that “fellow researchers that engage already in FAIR and open data practices” as well as “more detailed specifications and/or stronger requirements from research funders” are weak motivators (5%, 6%, respectively). Postdocs value “FAIR and open data practices playing a stronger role in internal evaluations” as the strongest motivator (63%) and “awards for FAIR & open data practices” as the least important motivator (55%). Ph D. students also rank “awards for FAIR & open data practices” less important (24%), but, in stark opposition to postdocs, value “FAIR and open data practices playing a stronger role in internal evaluations” as the least important motivator (22%).

4 Data sharing

4.1 Drivers for data sharing

4.1.1 Results

Figure 14: Bar chart of answers to the question “How important are the following drivers for you to share your data?”

Table 7: Free text entries for the field “How important are the following drivers for you to share your data?... [Other]”.

How important are the following drivers for you to share your data?... [Other]: free text entries

- (1) We might not be able to collect data in certain areas due to political and/or environmental restrictions (scientific marine research)!
- (2) Cuts in the research budget might result in reusing legacy data.
- (3) FAIR data enables AI.
Allows for worldwide and syntheses studies.
Enable adaption and re-purposing of research output (“frugal innovation”)
enhance reliability of research outputs
European and German law
It's fun :)

Figure 15: Bar chart of answers to the question “How important are the following drivers for you to share your data?”. Only answers “very important” and “important”, ordered in terms of percentage of answers.

How important are the following drivers for you to share your data?

Figure 16: Bar chart of answers to the question “How important are the following drivers for you to share your data?”. Only answers “very important” and “important” (see Fig. 15, calculated to 100%, grey bars in the background), combined with status information of the participants.

4.1.2 Discussion

For researchers, FAIR and open data practices may comprise a variety of activities (see above, Introduction), with data sharing being a most central element of these practices (see, e.g., NFDI4Earth Consortium (2024)). This is especially true for researchers from natural sciences: considering different research disciplines, researchers from natural sciences regularly are reported to share data more willingly and often than researchers from other disciplines (Tenopir *et al.* 2020; Enwald *et al.* 2022).

Rationales for sharing research data as well as researchers’ practices, motivations and concerns for sharing their data have been subject of many studies (Borgman 2012; Fecher *et al.* 2015; Kratz and Strasser 2015; Kim and Stanton 2016; Chawinga and Zinn 2019; Iain *et al.* 2021; Tedersoo *et al.* 2021; Woods and Pinfield 2021; Gomes *et al.* 2022; Watson 2022; Kaiser and Brainard 2023) and has also been investigated for the Earth System Sciences (Tenopir *et al.* 2018; Radosavljevic *et al.* 2019; Wu and Worrall 2019; Yan *et al.* 2020; Gilder *et al.* 2021; Meistring 2023).

Better science

92% of the survey participants consider “better reuse of data” as a “very important” or “important” driver to share research data. 84% consider “the possibility of verification of research”, and 78% “more robust own research” as a “very important” or “important” driver to share research data (Fig. 16). These three most important factors may be summarised under the term ‘better science’. It emphasises that researchers are intrinsically motivated and primarily share data in order to advance science; external requirements of research funders, order to advance science; external requirements of research funders, journals, institutional policies or community norms play a less important role (see below).

This is consistent with identified benefits of data sharing in a study by (Chawinga and Zinn 2019), investigating 105 studies on data sharing: “Nearly all articles, that is 104 (99%), highlighted that data sharing advances science, ...” (Chawinga and Zinn 2019). A survey at Earth Science institutions in Germany underpins these results: there is high approval of survey participants that data are a very important element of scientific work and do improve trust of the society in scientific findings (Meistring 2023).

Higher visibility in the research community

Higher visibility in the research community is a “very important” or “important” driver for data sharing, as reported by 72% of the survey participants. Increased visibility can have several benefits for researchers, including improving their reputation and credibility within the field. When researchers share data, they are able to demonstrate their expertise and contribute to the advancement of knowledge in their field. This can lead to increased recognition and respect from their peers, which can be beneficial for their career advancement. Sharing data can lead to increased citations and references, and sharing data can also lead to increased collaboration and networking opportunities.

Requirements from publishers, funders, institutions, and data sharing norms

The expectations of publishers, funders, research institutions, and research communities regarding data publishing are important drivers for data sharing, as reported by 64-67% of survey participants (Fig. 15). This finding is consistent with other studies, which have highlighted the significant role that research funding agencies play in encouraging researchers to share their research data (Chawinga and Zinn 2019). By setting clear expectations and providing incentives for data sharing, publishers, funders, research institutions, and research communities can help to create a culture of openness and transparency that values the sharing and reuse of research data.

Major STEM publishers such as Elsevier, Springer Nature, and Wiley have implemented data

policies that promote data sharing.⁸ Research has shown that such policies can have a positive impact on data sharing (Woods and Pinfield 2021).

However, while these policies are a step in the right direction, there is still room for improvement. Researchers have called for more comprehensive and effective data policies (Roche 2016; Christian *et al.* 2020), and efforts have been made to develop better policies and guidelines for data sharing (Hrynaszkiewicz *et al.* 2020), also for the Earth System Sciences⁹. Specifically, for journals published by German learned societies or research institutions, there is an opportunity to improve data policy presence and quality, particularly for journals in the Earth Sciences and biodiversity (Hübner 2020).

Institutional research data policies are now a common feature of many universities and research institutions, including those in Germany¹⁰. In fact, all member universities and research institutions of the NFDI4Earth consortium have established policies related to research data management. However, a closer examination of these policies reveals that they often lack specificity and detail, leaving researchers uncertain about what is expected of them.

This lack of clarity and detail in institutional research data policies highlights the need for more education and training on data publication, as well as stronger efforts to disseminate community norms and guidelines. The NFDI4Earth Commitment Statement (NFDI4Earth Consortium 2024) and the Commitment Statement To Enabling Fair Data In The Earth, Space, And Environmental Sciences (Enabling FAIR Data Community 2018) are dedicated to playing a strong role in this respect, providing guidance on community norms related to data publication and helping to promote a culture of openness and collaboration.

Disciplinary data sharing norms play an important role as incentives for data sharing. The Coalition for Publishing Data in the Earth and Space Sciences (COPDESS) and the Enabling FAIR Data initiative have developed statements on data sharing that provide a framework for researchers to follow. (COPDESS 2014; Enabling FAIR Data Community 2018). Additionally, the NFDI4Earth has published the NFDI4Earth Fairness and Openness Commitment. (NFDI4Earth Consortium 2024). The challenge ahead for NFDI4Earth is to foster uptake of the messages conveyed with this commitment statement.

Citations, duplicate data collection, Invitations to co-authorships

For 56% of the survey participants, receiving more citations of their research papers is a motivator for data sharing, ranking as a "very important" or "important" driver. This is not

⁸ <https://www.elsevier.com/about/policies-and-standards/research-data>; <https://authorservices.wiley.com/author-resources/Journal-Authors/open-access/data-sharing-citation/data-sharing-policy.html>; <https://www.springernature.com/de/authors/research-data-policy> (accessed 05 April 2025)

⁹ <https://copdess.org/enabling-fair-data-project/author-guidelines/> (accessed 05 April 2025)

¹⁰ https://www.forschungsdaten.org/index.php/Data_Policies (accessed 05 April 2025)

surprising, given the significant emphasis placed on citation metrics in the evaluation of researchers, such as the h-index in internal assessments and hiring processes.

However, the relatively low ranking of this statement by survey participants may be due to a lack of confidence in the effectiveness of data publications in increasing citations of related journal articles. This is understandable, given the complexity of the relationship between data sharing and citation impact. Despite this scepticism, research has shown that there is a positive correlation between articles that include statements linking to data in a repository and higher citation impact. A study by (Colavizza *et al.* 2020) found that articles with such statements had an average citation impact that was 25.36% higher than articles without such statements.

The survey results indicate that “prevention of duplicate data collection” and “invitations to co-authorships from others that use my data” are significant drivers for data sharing, with 55% and 47% of respondents, respectively, considering them to be “very important” or “important” motivators (Fig. 15). While these drivers may rank at the lower end of the list of motivators in this survey section, it is essential to note that they still hold a significant level of importance, with approximately 50% of respondents considering them to be important.

Differences of status groups

When examining the responses of different status groups to the question, it may be noted that participants from the “professor” status group tend to view “invitations to co-authorships from others that use my data” as a less important motivator for data sharing, with only 6% indicating it as a “very important” or “important” driver (Fig. 16). In contrast, PhD students place a greater emphasis on invitations to co-authorships, with 32% indicating it as a “very important” or “important” driver (Fig. 16). This suggests that PhD students may be more motivated by the potential for co-authorships and collaborations, which can provide opportunities for networking, skill-building, and career advancement.

Additionally, it is obvious that “making society better informed” is a weaker motivator for professors and a stronger motivator for PhD students. This suggests that professors may be less motivated by the potential for their research to have a positive impact on society, while PhD students may be more driven by the desire to contribute to the greater good. PhD students may be more likely to be influenced by the desire to make a positive impact on society, as they are often at the beginning of their careers and may be more idealistic about the potential of their research to make a difference.

While there are some more differences in the importance-ranking of different status groups, these differences are generally less pronounced, especially not regarding the responses of the most important motivators

Free text entries

Free text entries for the survey field “How important are the following drivers for you to share your data?... [Other]” point out further incentives for data sharing (Tab. 7). These free text

entries provide additional insights into the drivers for sharing data, including the importance of FAIR data for enabling AI [artificial intelligence], facilitating worldwide and synthesis studies, and enhancing the reliability of research outputs. They also highlight the role of law and regulation in requiring the sharing of research data.

4.2 Barriers for data sharing

4.2.1 Results

Figure 17: Bar chart of answers to the question “How important are the following reasons for you to not share your data?”

Table 8: Free text entries for the field “How important are the following reasons for you to not share your data?... [Other]”.

How important are the following reasons for you to not share your data?... [Other]: free text entries

(1) Takes time, which I do not have and am not paid for. (2) Starting proper data sharing needs resources to implement standards for meta-data or to merge meta-data standards to own data. (3) Formats for data sharing are either not defined or are not applicable to my data-sets. I simply do not know, what to share (huge binary data sets or interpreted data tables?). I work in a group that develops new monitoring tools, and as such has very unique data sets...

a lot of work

How important are the following reasons for you to not share your data?... [Other]: free text entries

Adding sufficient documentation and metadata is time consuming.

Becoming legally vulnerable in case of misuse or other problems

Being scooped by organizations with more manpower and resources is a real threat that should not be underestimated, and I have witnessed that in connection with gross misinterpretation and miserable science, which is then also bad for the reputation of the data set itself.

Comment on "Concerns about misinterpretation or misuse of data": Therefore, data descriptor papers should be accompanied by potentially misinterpretatable data.

data might be so specific that there might not be common interest in them

data preliminary, missing QC and hence not published.

For a very massive amount of modeling data, it can be a real drag if we have to adjust the data format and add, by the community required, metadata information. Sometimes the labor resources are not always available.

I don't think these questions are properly phrased. What is the correct answer to "I am not aware of a suitable data repository" when I am aware of repositories, but I don't want to store data in them?

If "data sharing" here includes "software code": I do not think, multi-year efforts in writing software code should be shared within a single click.

It happened to me that my repositories were cited and not the accompanying publications themselves. One time not even due to an error of the authors, but the journal changed the reference list during typesetting cancelling the paper citation and leaving only the data and code doi. That is very unpleasant considering that only the paper citations are accounted in research metrics.

It takes a lot of time to prepare the metadata and the actual data submission: important

Like to emphasise that main barrier in our research field is content protection (e.g. occurrence of endangered species or economically minerals), however, techniques like blurring of data points can often be applied.

Makes the publishing process more time consuming. There are already so many forms to fill

no resources (esp. time)

no standard data format, very complicated to bring data in useable format for other researchers, as data acquisition is complex and non-standard with inhouse developed unique equipment

Research work is still carried out and needs first to be published until data should be available. This is in particular important for Ph.D. projects.

Security reasons, intellectual property protection, commercial interest

Technical challenges: the data I generate (spatially resolved maps and point measurements located on a sample surface (often thin sections) is hard to sensibly archive, as it would be very important to preserve *where* on the sample the data was taken with high precision, with relation to an overview image and other spatially resolved datasets from the same sample. This is currently not available.

There are no reasons for not sharing data as research is funded by taxes unless data has been paid by companies not bound by law to publish.

There is still no good way to share terabytes of model output. Thus, we always have to extract data for a few variables (those used in publications) rather than sharing all of the model output. It would be valuable if there were a repository where all raw model output could be uploaded.

Too large data sets to be fully shared on a public repository

volume of data

Figure 18: Bar chart of answers to the question “How important are the following reasons for you to not share your data?”. Only answers “very important” and “important”, ordered in terms of percentage of answers.

How important are the following reasons for you to not share your data?

Figure 19: Bar chart of answers to the question “How important are the following reasons for you to not share your data?”. Only answers “very important” and “important” (see Fig. 18, calculated to 100%, grey bars in the background), combined with status information of the participants.

4.2.2 Discussion

Data are not suitable for sharing

The most important barrier to data sharing is the “data are not suitable for sharing” (Fig. 19), which comes as a surprise. The answer option in the survey suggests especially sensitive data to be unsuitable for sharing. The Earth Sciences are not a typical discipline with major sensitive data production, as compared, e.g. the social sciences. The sub-discipline of human geography is an exception where qualitative research methods are often applied and where sharing faces conceptual and ethical challenges (Lamb *et al.* 2024). However, it is worth noting that researchers from human geography did not take part in this survey.

Spatial data in the Earth, environmental and agricultural sciences and some solid Earth data may be difficult to share openly because they may contain sensitive data (Hartmann 2019) or due to ethical reasons related to natural and anthropogenic hazards and risk communication (Cocco *et al.* 2025). But these exceptions only concern sub-areas of the Earth System Sciences.

Business interests can lead to contractual obligations that may hinder data sharing. This applies mainly to projects with industry collaborations. However, although Earth System

Sciences research includes applied science as well as basic research, Earth System Sciences is not a discipline that is exceptionally strong in industrial co-operation, like e.g. Engineering Sciences (Kotiranta *et al.* 2020).

As the importance of this barrier cannot be convincingly explained by the frequent occurrence of sensitive data or particularly frequent industrial cooperation in the Earth System Sciences compared to other disciplines, it can be assumed that other reasons contribute to the participants' perception that data are not suitable of sharing, including the other ones addressed with this question in the current survey (see below).

Fear of being scooped

Scoping is the second most important reason to not share data (only answers “very important” and “important”: 40%). The fear of being scooped by someone else is a significant concern for researchers, particularly for PhD students and early career scientists. This fear can be a major barrier to data sharing, as researchers may be hesitant to share their data in case someone else publishes similar research before them. It's essential to acknowledge and recognise this fear, rather than dismissing it as an irrational concern. By acknowledging the fear of being scooped, it may be addressed in a more constructive way (Paschetto *et al.* 2024).

Fortunately, the risk of being scooped by someone else is relatively low, especially for researchers who have invested time and effort in collecting data and developing code: as Gomes *et al.* (2022) note, those who have invested in their research are often best equipped to build upon and analyse their own work.

To counteract the fear of being scooped, researchers may find it helpful to use instruments such as (a) appropriate credit for data collection, curation, and publication (this can help to ensure that researchers receive recognition for their work and are not unfairly scooped by others) or (b) carefully chosen access embargoes (may help to control the flow of data and ensure that researchers have a reasonable amount of time to publish their research before others can access the data). By using these instruments, researchers can feel more confident in sharing their data.

Misuse of data

Misuse of research data is related to scooping in that it is a fear that can create obstacles to the open sharing and reuse of data. The term “misuse” can encompass a wide range of behaviours, including unintentional errors, unauthorised reuse, and intentional manipulation. (Parquet *et al.* 2024).

Unintentional errors, such as methodological mistakes during replication, can occur when researchers are unaware of the complexities of the research object or fail to properly understand its context. Unauthorised reuse of research objects, such as using data or materials without consent, can also be considered misuse. This can occur when researchers

fail to obtain proper permissions or neglect to acknowledge the original creators of the research object. Intentional manipulation of research objects, such as referring to them in misleading ways to influence public opinion, is also a form of misuse. This can be particularly problematic when it involves distorting or misrepresenting the findings of a study to achieve a particular agenda.

According to Pasquetto et al (2024) and references therein, scientists' concerns about data misuse can be broadly categorised into three main areas:

- Fear of being scooped or losing credit for their data collection efforts: This fear arises from the possibility that others may use their data without proper citation or recognition, potentially undermining their own research and reputation.
- Fear of reusers making mistakes or errors in secondary analysis: This fear is driven by concerns that others may misinterpret or misuse the data, leading to incorrect conclusions or flawed research. This can be due to a variety of factors, including poor data quality or the complexity of the data.
- Fear of replication experiments: This fear is rooted in the possibility that others may replicate the original research and discover flaws or errors that were not apparent in the original study.

The lack of contextual information about a dataset and its meaning is often cited as a common source of data misuse (excluding cases of intentional misuse). To address this issue, curating and documenting data is a key intervention to prevent inappropriate and unwanted uses of open research data (Wilkinson *et al.* 2016). This is because documentation provides essential context and meaning to a dataset, enabling users to understand its limitations, biases, and potential applications.

Lack of knowledge and information

A significant barrier to data sharing among survey participants is the lack of knowledge about community expectations regarding the full description and licensing of a dataset, with 38% citing this as a major obstacle. This lack of knowledge is the third most important barrier, indicating that there is a need for education and awareness-raising on this topic.

Interestingly, other barriers related to a lack of information, such as not knowing where to publish data (32%) and not knowing how to share data (16%), rank lower in importance. This suggests that basic knowledge about data publication is present in the research community, but that there are still uncertainties and gaps in knowledge about specific aspects of data publication.

This lack of knowledge and information highlights the need for more education and training on data publication, as well as stronger efforts to disseminate community norms and guidelines. The NFDI4Earth Commitment Statement (NFDI4Earth Consortium 2024) and the Commitment

Statement To Enabling Fair Data In The Earth, Space, And Environmental Sciences (Enabling FAIR Data Community 2018) are dedicated to playing a strong role in this respect, providing guidance on community norms related to data publication and helping to promote a culture of openness and collaboration.

Career advantages

Data sharing has currently little impact on career advancement of researchers, shown for example by the fact that this practice plays hardly ever a role in promotion, review and tenure (PRT) documents of research institutions (see e.g. (Pontika *et al.* 2021). However, for the participants of this survey, only a small share (about 25%) consider a lack of career advancement by data sharing practices an important barrier for data sharing. This is in line with participant's answers to the question about motivators for data sharing: Higher visibility in the research community, which may be related to improvement of researcher's reputation and credibility within the field, and thus, career advancement, is a "very important" or "important" driver for data sharing for a high number (72%) of the survey participants.

When, instead of data sharing, FAIR and open data practices are considered, career advantage play a less important role as a motivator: compared to other motivators in this section, career-related answers rank in the middle to lower range (Fig. 12). This may be due to the fact that, whenever researchers discuss FAIR and open data practices, data sharing is in the focus as the most familiar and well know FAIR and open data practices. Other practices like using data management plans, supporting development of open and FAIR standards and practices as well as educating colleagues in practices that enable open and FAIR research outputs are maybe much less obvious practices.

Initiatives like DORA (DORA Steering Committee 2012), the Leiden manifesto (Hicks *et al.* 2015) or, more recently, CoARA¹¹, work towards changes in assessment practices for research and researchers. They all call for a recognition of a variety of practices and activities to be included in research assessment, and with that, promote strongly data sharing. In this respect it is important to recognise that many of the NFDI4Earth research institutions have signed the CoARA declaration and thus committed to review their research assessment procedures and develop measures to improve them (Tab. 6).

Differences of status groups

Taking status group differences into consideration (Fig. 19), it shows that professors may have a stronger perception that data is not suitable for sharing. This may be due to the fact that data sharing is a relatively new concept that was not discussed or practiced when they were early-career scientists. On the other hand, PhD students today typically receive education on data management, including data sharing, and may be better informed about the conditions

¹¹ <https://coara.eu/> (accessed 05 April 2025)

and possibilities of data sharing. Considering career advantages, especially Postdocs think that data publications are not career advancing.

Free text entries

The free text entries for the question “How important are the following reasons for you to not share your data?... [Other]” highlight additional barriers to data sharing, as listed in Table 8. The most significant issue mentioned is the lack of time to share data, specifically the time needed to properly prepare the data for publication and reuse.

However, as noted in the literature, the initial effort required to share research data and code can ultimately reduce burdens for individual researchers and their colleagues, while also benefiting others who seek to reuse it. Moreover, taking the time to properly annotate and organise data and code can provide significant benefits for future projects (Gomes et al., 2022).

A significant challenge arises in the Earth System Sciences from the scarcity of suitable storage solutions for vast amounts of data, such as model output. A recent survey of members of the Faculty of Science, University of Potsdam, confirms these findings. The Geosciences group was the most prominent in indicating that uncertainties about the long-term availability of repositories are an important barrier to data sharing (Riedel et al., 2024). Some survey participants also mentioned concerns about misinterpretation or misuse of data, concerns about intellectual property protection and about commercial interests.

5 Conclusions

The results of this survey prove that researchers think that FAIR and open data is an important concept which should be expanded. Towards this end, researchers are already today engaged in a large variety of FAIR and open data practice, although to a different extent. NFDI4Earth may take the survey results as an opportunity to strengthen motivators for FAIR & open data practices in general and, in particular, for data publication that are of high importance of survey participants. At the same time, barrier of high importance to survey participants may be assessed in order to identify targeted future actions to phase out disincentivising environments and structures. NFDI4Earth might form strategic partnerships with partners like academic societies or the FID GEO for joint projects to improve the adoption of FAIR and open data practice.

Developments of data citation metrics and the recognition of FAIR and open data practices are, at the national and international level, still in their infancy. NFDI4Earth supports the cultural change towards more FAIR and open data practices and more variable research evaluation with the NFDI4Earth FAIRness and Openness Commitment, with its work with academic societies and with looking into existing rewarding systems for FAIR and open data practices. Such activities accompany and support the implementation of initiatives like CoARA which tackle these issues at a broader scale and in a wider context (many of the NFDI4Earth member institutions are already CoARA members). Appropriate credit for data collection, curation and publication may be a well-suited instrument to counteract the fear of being scooped.

Answers about career-related indicators in the “data sharing” sections of this survey support the fact that researchers do consider career advantages as rather weak motivator for FAIR and open data practices. This may simply reflect the current reality: to date, FAIR and open data practices do play only minor or, mostly, no roles in the hiring, tenure or promotion processes. Again, CoARA is a major player addressing these issues and should be supported strongly by NFDI4Earth member institutions.

It is notable that the three most important drivers for data publication mentioned by survey participants can be summarised in the perception that data sharing improves science as a whole. This indicates that data sharing is a highly valued practice in principle. Together with the fact that, in praxi, data sharing is not yet the default for many researchers today, NFDI4Earth may concentrate on training and education on data sharing as well as working together with NFDI4Earth member institutions and other partners to promote the introduction of data sharing policies and to strengthen existing data sharing policies.

The fact that colleagues as role models are important motivators for FAIR and open data practices may inform NFDI4Earth member institutions to develop programs that make researchers that engage in FAIR and open data practice more visible, e.g. by the introduction of data champions.

Only few participants think that awards for FAIR and open data practices are strong motivators. NFDI4Earth member institutions or academic societies may take this result as a hint to design awards very carefully and to not overrate this instrument.

When looking at the barriers for data sharing, supporting training and education activities is thought to be the most effective way to counteract these barriers. This is especially true in the light of the fact that the technical infrastructure to share data in the Earth System Sciences is already present today. Additionally, appropriate credit for data publication should be implemented by NFDI4Earth member institutions.

The most important reason for not sharing data is the consideration of survey participants that the data are not suitable for sharing. The high importance of this barrier cannot be explained easily (see above); it may be speculated that the perception that data is not suitable for sharing is feeling that stems from a mixture of reasons, including unfamiliarity with data publishing, fears of being scooped and a general notion that “my data” must not be shared with others.

NFDI4Earth member institutions should take advantage of NFDI4Earth-developed instruments in order to provide better assistance and infrastructure to its researchers: educational resources, training opportunities, and the results of short-term projects (pilots, incubators) to develop specific solutions and explore new concepts can be used by institutions to improve local research support. Development of central NFDI4Earth services like the OneStopForAll and the Living Handbook, to be used by all Earth System Sciences researchers, add to the bundle of NFDI4Earth support instruments used by institutions for their researchers. In this way, the core outputs of NFDI4Earth may develop in the future into strong support instruments for researchers to improve and extend FAIR and open data practices.

It is important for NFDI4Earth to set up and run its services at a high quality, so that researchers are convinced to use them. One aspect to increase the acceptance of these instruments is that they may be developed and tested also by researchers themselves to ensure that they meet their needs. They must be user-friendly and not add additional complexity for researchers to use them. Effective communication of these instruments within the research community will be crucial to ensure that researchers know that they exist, how to use them and how to benefit from them.

NFDI4Earth individual members in their various roles as researcher, members of data infrastructure units or research data management teams may take action at their home research institutions and try to identify own activities from this survey that may render success especially under the local conditions of their research institutions.

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